

Author's accepted version

Histopathological and molecular effects of microplastics in *Eisenia andrei* Bouché.

Cite this article as:

Rodriguez-Seijo A, Lourenço J, Rocha-Santos TAP, da Costa J, Duarte AC, Vala H, Pereira R. Histopathological and molecular effects of microplastics in *Eisenia andrei* Bouché. Environmental Pollution 220, 495-503. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.09.092>

The full version can be found at ScienceDirect (Elsevier) <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.09.092>

Histopathological and molecular effects of microplastics in

Eisenia andrei

¹Rodríguez-Seijo, A., ²Lourenço, J., ³Rocha-Santos, T.A.P., ³da Costa, J., ³Duarte, A. C.,
^{4,5}Vala, H., ⁶Pereira, R.*

¹Department of Plant Biology and Soil Science, Universidade de Vigo, As Lagoas, Marcosende, 36310 Vigo, Spain.

²Department of Biology & CESAM, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

³Department of Chemistry & CESAM, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

⁴Agrarian School of Viseu, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu. Viseu, Portugal

⁵Centre for the Research and Technology of Agro-Environmental and Biological Sciences (CITAB and Centre for Studies in Education, and Health Technologies (CI&DETS), Portugal

⁶Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences of the University of Porto & CIIMAR - Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research & GreenUP/CITAB-UP, Porto, Portugal

Corresponding author

Ruth Pereira

Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences of the University of Porto

Rua do Campo Alegre s/n

4169-007 Porto

Portugal

Phone number:+351 220402746

E-mail: ruth.pereira@fc.up.pt

Molecular effects

Histopathological effects

Highlights

- Earthworms may be able to selectively ingest microplastics and/or to egest them.
- Serious histological damages in the gut of earthworms were observed.
- Molecular changes in the body of earthworms point for possible immune system responses.
- Hystopathological analyses also showed serious signs of gut inflammation.
- Immune system responses seemed to be related with those to deal with strange bodies.

1 **Abstract**

2 The ocean has been assumed as the main sink of microplastics (MPs), however, soils may also
3 receive MPs from different sources and through different pathways, which may affect the biota
4 and their role in soil functions. To the best of our knowledge, only one study, until now,
5 reported the effects of MPs on the survival and fitness of soil organisms (*Lumbricus terrestris*).
6 In our study, epigeic earthworms, of the species *Eisenia andrei*, were exposed to different
7 concentrations of MPs (0, 62.5, 125, 250, 500 and 1000 mg kg⁻¹ soil_{dw}) in an OECD artificial
8 soil and tested for reproduction, survival and growth of adults, following a standard protocol.
9 The size of the polyethylene MPs to which earthworms were exposed ranged between 250 and
10 1000 µm. No significant effects were recorded on survival, number of juveniles and, in the final
11 weight of adult earthworms after 28d of exposure, to the different concentrations of MPs.
12 Nevertheless, FTIR-ATR of earthworms and histopathological analysis of the gut provided
13 evidences of damages and immune system responses to MPs.

14

15

16 Capsule: This is one of the first studies assessing the effects of microplastics on terrestrial
17 earthworms and it provides evidence of tissue damage in the gut and immune system responses.

18

19 Key Words: microplastics, *Eisenia andrei*, FTIR-ATR, histopathology, reproduction, soil

20 **Introduction**

21 Although the ocean (water column and deep sea sediments included) has been identified as a
22 major sink for MPs (Cózar et al., 2014; Woodall et al., 2014), soils also represent an important
23 sink of these contaminants (Dris et al., 2016; Espí et al., 2006; Lassen et al., 2015; Ramos et al.,
24 2015; Rillig, 2012). However, the distribution of MPs in soils, both quantitatively and
25 qualitatively, as well as their spatial distribution on soils with different uses, has not been
26 studied so far (Rillig, 2012). As pointed out by Rillig (2012), this may be due to: 1) the
27 difficulties associated to the extraction and quantification of microplastics in a complex organo-
28 mineral matrix like soil and, 2) the absence of a pattern of accumulation like that found along
29 shorelines. MPs can accumulate in soils due to the great use of greenhouses, walk-in tunnels,
30 low tunnel and mulching covers applied in agriculture, sewage sludge applications (for soil
31 fertilization or remediation) and by deterioration of outdoor plastic structures and painted
32 surfaces (Espí et al., 2006; Lassen et al., 2015; Ramos et al., 2015; Rillig, 2012; Steinmetz et al.,
33 2016). MPs can also enter the atmosphere and reach soils through deposition processes (Rocha-
34 Santos and Duarte, 2015). Dris and co-authors (2016), in a work performed on an urban area of
35 Paris, found synthetic fibers in atmospheric fallout, thereby confirming the presence of MPs in
36 all environmental compartments and a possible source of MPs to urban soils. Additionally, the
37 possibility of MPs being windblown from landfills and recycling facilities (Duis and Coors,
38 2016; Rillig, 2012) was also mentioned. Terrestrial organisms like earthworms may also
39 contribute to secondary MPs formation, as they can ingest brittle plastics debris and turn them
40 into microplastics (Rillig, 2012). These and other organisms, such as collembolan or mites and
41 even gophers or moles, may also contribute not only to the degradation of surface-deposited
42 plastic particulates, but also to their incorporation into the soil (Lambert et al., 2014; Rillig,
43 2012).

44 The potential of MP to cause harm on marine invertebrates has been widely documented (e.g.
45 Besseling et al., 2013; Browne et al., 2013; Claessens et al., 2011; Green et al., 2016; von Moos
46 et al., 2012; Wright et al., 2013). Few studies focused on freshwater invertebrates (e.g. Au et al.,

47 2015; Ogonowski et al., 2016) and only one study, until now, reported the ingestion and the
48 effects of MPs on terrestrial earthworms (Lwanga et al., 2016). However, negative effects are
49 expected to occur in soil organisms as well (Duis and Coors, 2016; Lassen et al., 2015; Rillig,
50 2012). Many soil-dwelling organisms feed in the same way as sediment-dwelling organisms (for
51 example, ciliates and rotifers living in thin films of water covering soil surfaces and in soil
52 pores), making reasonable the assumption of similar exposure routes and potential effects
53 (Lassen et al., 2015; Rillig, 2012). Moreover, geophagous soil fauna, like earthworms, can also
54 ingest MPs, as well as other micro- and mesofauna thus contributing for their transference in the
55 soil detrital food web (Rillig, 2012) and possibly for destabilizing important soil functions and
56 services.

57 In order to evaluate the effects of microplastics in soil-dwelling organisms, earthworms
58 (*Eisenia andrei* Bouché, 1972) were exposed to a reference soil mixed with MPs, and effects on
59 growth and reproduction were followed according to, the OECD TG 222 (2004) protocol.
60 Moreover, molecular modifications and the occurrence of histopathological alterations were
61 pursued to determine the effects of MP at the molecular, tissue and individual level.
62 Earthworms were selected for this study because they are an important model test species used
63 in several standard ecotoxicological tests (ISO, 1996; OECD, 2004, 1984), but also due to their
64 importance in maintaining soil structure and permeability, as well as in the degradation of
65 organic matter (Button et al., 2010; Lavelle et al., 1997).

66

67

68 **2. Materials and Methods**

69 **2.1. Microplastics**

70 In this study, polyethylene pellets (C₂H₄)_n from Sigma-Aldrich [CAS Number 9002-88-4, linear
71 low density, melt index 25 g/10 min (190°C/2.16kg)], with a diameter of ≈5000 μm were used.
72 These polyethylene (PE) pellets were mechanically cut in a mill (made by hand in workshops of
73 the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Porto - figure A1 and A2 in supplementary

74 material) and the resulting fragments sieved on a calibrated vibratory sieve shaker Retsch
75 AS200 to obtain particles with a size range of $250 < \text{MP} < 1000 \mu\text{m}$. The average number of
76 MP per 100 mg was estimated as 396 ± 52 (STDEV) by counting and weighting ten different
77 portions of MP. MPs were characterized by Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectrometry with
78 Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR), as well as by optic and electronic microscopy
79 (section 2.2. for more details). In Figure 1A, the typical FTIR spectrum of this material is shown
80 and, in Figures 1B and 1C, representative images obtained by optical (amplification x100) and
81 electronic microscopy are shown, respectively. FTIR-ATR analyses were carried out using a
82 Perkin Elmer (USA) Spectrum BX FTIR instrument. Samples were analysed at a 4 cm^{-1}
83 resolution within the 4000 – 550 nm range.

84 In summary, Figure 1B shows an optical microscope image of the MPs added to OECD
85 soil and to the positive control (CTL) flasks with agar (amplification 100X). This image
86 exemplifies one of the shapes of MPs obtained for the test. Further, it helped identifying MPs
87 within the gut of earthworms in the histological slides, mainly based on their optical hue.

88

89 *Please insert figure 1A, B, C*

90 **2.2. Morphological analysis of MPs**

91 Optical microscopy was carried out using a Carl Zeiss Axiovert 40 MAT microscope (Carl
92 Zeiss Light Microscopy, Göttingen, Germany). The samples were prepared by direct deposition
93 of aliquots on glass slides. For digestive tract content analyses, worms were thoroughly washed
94 with deionized water and longitudinal cuts were done. Samples (of MPs and of earthworm's gut
95 content) were studied using an Olympus BX51 microscope. Three adult earthworms were
96 randomly selected for analysis of gut content, from each replicate (both from the treatments +
97 CTL) of the reproduction assay (please see section 2.5.). Detailed morphological analyzes of
98 MPs were performed using a Field Emission Gun (FEG) - SEM Hitachi S4100 microscope
99 (Japan), operated at 15 kV. The samples were prepared by deposition, directly onto the carbon
100 tape and then, coated by carbon evaporation (Emitech K950X, France).

101

102 **2.3. Test substrate**

103 The OECD artificial soil (OECD, 2004) was used as a test substrate. It was prepared, according
104 to the OECD guideline 222 (OECD, 2004), by mixing sphagnum peat, kaolin clay and air-dried
105 quartz sand in the proportions recommended to obtain a soil with 5% of organic matter. Soil pH
106 was adjusted with calcium carbonate to 6.0 ± 0.5 . Afterwards, water-holding capacity (WHC)
107 was determined according to, ISO guidelines (ISO, 2008, 1998). Soil water content (%) was
108 measured by determining soils weight loss after drying at 105°C, for 24h. The water content of
109 the soil was taken into account to adjust soil moisture to 40% of WHC_{max} . Soil pH_{H_2O} was
110 measured according to, the method described by FAOUN (1984) in a soil-water suspension (1:5
111 w/v extraction ratio).

112

113

114 **2.4. Test organisms**

115 The earthworms used in this study belong to the species *Eisenia andrei* Bouché and were
116 obtained from a synchronized laboratorial culture, reared in large containers, under controlled
117 conditions (photoperiod 16h^L:8h^D; temperature $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) as described by Gavina and co-authors
118 (2016). Briefly, the substrate used for the culture was composed by sphagnum peat, dry and
119 defaunated horse manure and CaCO_3 to adjust the pH between 6 and 7. The substrate was
120 periodically moistened with distilled water and the pH monitored. The organisms were fed with
121 oat flakes once a week. For the tests, the adult earthworms selected exhibited clitellum and a
122 body mass between 250 and 600 mg, as recommended by international guidelines (ISO, 1998;
123 OECD, 2004). Prior to the tests, the earthworms were acclimatized, for 24 h, in test containers
124 with the OECD artificial soil, under the same conditions described for culture maintenance.

125

126 **2.5. Laboratorial exposure of earthworms and reproduction assay**

127 The reproduction assay was performed according the OECD guideline 222 (2004) under the
128 same conditions (light/dark cycle and temperature) previously described for laboratorial
129 cultures. The OECD soil was thoroughly mixed with MPs at final concentrations of 62.5, 125,
130 250, 500, 1000 mg MPs kg soil_{dw}⁻¹. A negative CTL, with OECD soil without MPs was also
131 included. Four replicates were prepared per treatment and 10 earthworms were randomly
132 selected, weighted and placed in each test container (polypropylene pots with a volume of about
133 1500 cm³) with 500g_{dw} of artificial soil. After 28 days of exposure, adults were gently extracted
134 from the test vessels by hand sorting, weighted and then treated for the following
135 histopathological, microscopy and FTIR analyses (please see section 2.2, 2.6). At the end of the
136 reproduction assay, (56 days) juveniles were removed from the containers and, counted.

137

138 **2.6. Histopathology and FTIR-ATR analysis**

139 For histopathological analyses, adult earthworms from the reproduction assay were left to
140 dehydrate for 24h in moisturized filtered paper. At the end of the dehydration period, all the
141 earthworms were placed in a 4% formaldehyde (= 10% buffered formalin solution) (pH=7.0 ±
142 0.2) Prolabo®, and kept there for at least 24h.

143 In order to obtain a positive CTL, in which earthworms had the possibility to ingest
144 MPs non-mixed with soil particles, additional organisms (from the same culture) were
145 dehydrated for 24h in wet filter paper and then placed in agar, according to, the protocol
146 described by Pokarzhevskii and co-authors (2000) with slight modifications. Briefly, 100 mL
147 flasks were filled with 60 mL of a 1.5% agar media prepared with deionized water. After
148 cooling in the flasks, the medium was cut into small pieces and 2 earthworms were placed in
149 each flask. Twenty flasks were used, 10 without MP and 10 with MP (offered *ad libitum*). MPs
150 were mixed up with the agar. Five earthworms were maintained in the flasks, for 72 hours and
151 kept at 20°C. Afterwards, the animals were removed and preserved as described above for
152 histopathological analysis.

153 Two adult earthworms per replicate (both from the reproduction assays and from the
154 CTL with agar) were transversely cut in the medium part of body and then dehydrated (which
155 was done by transferring the tissue through solutions of increasing alcohol concentration, until
156 100% alcohol was reached), cleared with xylene (also universal paraffin solvent) and embedded
157 in paraffin wax. From these, 3 μm thick sections were obtained, placed on a slide,
158 deparaffinised (with xylene solution) and rehydrated (with decreasing alcohol concentration,
159 until 70% alcohol was reached). The slides were then stained with haematoxylin and eosin
160 (HE), performed with nuclear stain (Harris haematoxylin) for 8 minutes, submerged in water for
161 10 minutes and counterstained with 1% alcoholic eosin, in which samples remained for 6
162 minutes. To achieve dehydration, the reverse process was then performed, passing through
163 increasing alcohol concentrations and xylene. Finally, slides were cover slipped, using a
164 permanent mounting media. All slides were examined by light microscopy using a Microscope
165 Zeiss Mod. Axioplan 2. Image acquisition was performed with a digital microscope camera
166 (Leica DFC450) and image processing was performed with the LAS Advanced Analysis
167 Software Bundle (No: 12730448). A semi-quantitative rating for each slide ranging from grade
168 0 (G0: minimal/no damage) to G3 (severe and extensive damage) was assigned to the following
169 effects: inflammatory infiltrate, fibrosis, congestion.

170 From each replicate, six earthworms randomly selected and previously deparaffinised were
171 freeze-dried using a VirTis benchtop K lyophilizer and kept in a desiccator until use. Samples of
172 the whole body of earthworms were analysed by FTIR-ATR at a 4 cm^{-1} resolution within the
173 4000 – 550 cm^{-1} range.

174

175 **2.7 Statistical Analysis.**

176 One-Way ANOVA was performed to test for significant differences in the number of juveniles
177 and adult earthworms weight between treatments, after checking for homoscedasticity of
178 variances and for normality with Levene's and Shapiro-Wilk tests, respectively.

179 A principal component analysis was performed to reduce the different wavenumber
180 intervals (cm⁻¹) at which the FTIR ATR spectra was obtained in only two components, and use
181 these two components to perceive the relationship between earthworms exposed to the different
182 MPs concentrations, in terms of their biochemical composition. Both the univariate and the
183 multivariate analysis were performed with MINITAB 17.

184

185

186 **3. Results and Discussion**

187 The reproduction test with earthworms fulfilled all the validity criteria described in the OECD
188 222 protocol (OECD, 2004) (for more details please see table A1 in supplementary material).
189 No mortality was recorded in all the treatments and in the CTL soil after 28 days of exposure
190 (100% survival). Furthermore, adult earthworms reached the end of their exposure period
191 without significant differences in average body weight between treatments (including CTL)
192 (ANOVA: $F=1.14$, d.f. 18, 23; $p=0.377$). In fact, and when the percentage of weight loss
193 relatively to the CTL is calculated (Table A1 in supplementary material) a highest percentage of
194 weight loss was obtained for the highest concentrations. However, some data variability was
195 obtained which has probably prevent the existence of significant differences. After 56 days of
196 exposure, no significant differences were recorded in the average number of juveniles produced
197 by earthworms from the different MP treatments (ANOVA: $F=0.50$; d.f. 18, 23; $p=0.744$) (table
198 A1 in the supplementary material). To the best of our knowledge, only one study has reported
199 the effects of MPs in terrestrial earthworms, namely in *Lumbricus terrestris* (Lwanga et al.,
200 2016). Although these worms were exposed to MPs with a smaller size (<150 μm) than that in
201 our study, the authors did not observe effects on reproduction as well. An increase in mortality
202 (25%) was recorded only when MP were mixed with plant litter in a 60% proportion and after
203 60 days of exposure. Additionally, earthworms displayed a decrease in growth rate for all the
204 MPs treatments tested by these authors (but significantly different from the control, only for the
205 treatment with a proportion of MPs in plant litter equal or higher than 28%). In agreement with

206 our results, Green et al. (2016) also did not observe significant differences in weight loss for
207 *Arenicola marina*, a marine sediment engineer species, exposed for 31 days to a mixture of MPs
208 at concentrations of 0.02, 0.2 and 2% wet sediment weight, under a mesocosm experiment.
209 These authors tested different MPs (polylactic acid- PLA, high density polyethylene- HDPE
210 and, polyvinylchloride- PVC plastics) with a range and mean (\pm SE) diameter of particles [1.4-
211 707 and 235.7 (\pm 14.8) μ m for PLA, 2.5-316 and 102.6 (\pm 10.3) μ m for HDPE and 8.7-478 and
212 130.6 (\pm 12.9) μ m for PVC], which was within the range of sizes tested in this study, at the least
213 for the intermediate particles sizes.

214 To the best of our knowledge, there is no information about the concentration of MPs
215 on soils. Existing data for marine, coastal and freshwater sediments point for a great variability
216 between sites (beaches, harbours and offshores), as well as, for a great variability in data
217 expression, what makes comparisons even more difficult (e.g. Carson et al., 2011; Claessens et
218 al., 2011; Thompson et al., 2004). According to Carson et. al. (2011), for example, in highly
219 impacted beaches, MP (<10 mm) concentrations of 3% by weight are expected. In our study, a
220 maximum concentration of 0.1% by weight (MP< 1mm) of soil was tested which suggests that
221 our data could be ecologically relevant. On other studies, like the one from Claessens et al.
222 (2011), concentrations up to 7.21 mg/kg⁻¹ dry sediment (390.7 \pm 32.6 particles kg⁻¹ dry sediment),
223 were reported for Belgian marine sediments, which were well below our lowest tested
224 concentration (62.5 mg kg⁻¹ soil_{dw}, 247.6 number of particles kg⁻¹soil_{dw}) in terms of mass, but
225 not in terms of the number of particles. However, costal sediments may not be representative of
226 agriculture areas, where polyethylene plastic has been extensively used for mulching
227 techniques, especially in regions where this practice had a remarkable increase in the last
228 decades (Steinmetz et al., 2016).

229 Gut content slides showed MPs clearly visible in some test subjects obtained from the
230 reproduction assay, after 28 days of exposure (Figure 2). No MPs were found in the gut of
231 earthworms from the positive CTL with MPs in agar medium.

232 ***Please insert figure 2***

233 Histological slides also confirmed the presence of the MP in some earthworms, but they
234 were not found in all earthworms exposed to MPs (Figure 3c and figure B in supplementary
235 material). Although this could have occurred by chance, as the cuts were performed randomly,
236 two possibilities should be considered. Either 1) earthworms ingested all the MPs randomly and
237 even the larger ones were efficiently egested, especially during the starvation/depuration 24h-
238 period, or 2) earthworms avoided the ingestion of larger MP, and the smaller particles were
239 efficiently egested, especially during the starvation/depuration 24h-period.

240 Considering the former hypothesis, the size of the mouth of most earthworm species
241 from temperate regions is about 3 mm, which mechanically does not prevent the ingestion of all
242 the MPs (Shumway and Koide, 1994; Zaller and Saxler, 2007) tested in this study. However,
243 considering seed size, Clause et al. (2011) observed a significant and negative correlation
244 between seeds size and ingestion rate for two species [*Lumbricus terrestris* (anecic) and
245 *Satchellius mammalis* (epigeic)]. This correlation was similar for both species and the seeds
246 ingested at highest percentages by both species varied between 500-1500 μm in size. In fact,
247 debris within this size range were observed in the gut of earthworms retrieved from the test
248 (Figures 2 and 3c). Besseling et al. (2013) also observed that marine lugworms (*Arenicola*
249 *marina*) ingested polystyrene particles ≥ 400 and up to 1300 μm (after an exposure for 28d in
250 sediments with a concentration up to 7.4% by dry weight). These organisms were also able to
251 completely clean their guts after being kept overnight in beakers with clean water

252 Regarding the second hypothesis, several studies have pointed for the possible feeding
253 selectivity of earthworms not only based on size, but also on other organic material properties
254 (Curry and Schmidt, 2007). Also, a study with *Eisenia andrei* demonstrated that, at 20°C, the
255 retention time of gut content was 5.5h (Jager et al., 2003). Therefore, ingested MPs may have
256 been completely egested at the time of analysis, at least for those that were depurated. The
257 absence of MP in the gut of earthworms from the positive CTL (where they were expected),
258 supports the hypothesis of selective feeding and/or efficient egestion (especially when
259 earthworms only feed on agar). Lwanga et al. (2016) also suggested a selective egestion of MPs

260 by *Lumbricus terrestris*, based on changes on the proportion of MP with less than 50 μm in
261 casts. However, it was not the objective of these authors to analyse the selectivity of MPs
262 ingestion by earthworms. Nevertheless, the information about the ability of invertebrates to deal
263 with MPs is inconsistent between species as some studies point for their inability to egest MPs
264 (e.g. Besseling et al., 2013; Wright et al., 2013).

265 Several physical impacts of MP were suggested, but few demonstrated, for marine
266 invertebrates, as blockages throughout the gut or abrasions from sharp objects (Wright et al.,
267 2013). In this study, both physical (tissue damages) but also immune system responses were
268 observed. Histopathological damages were noted even at the lowest tested concentration of MPs
269 in the soil ($62.5 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil}_{\text{dw}}$) (Figure 3c), though these were more severe at the highest
270 concentrations, in comparison with animals from the CTL with OECD soil without MP (Figure
271 3a). In particular, gut damages were evident in the midsection of the earthworm's body, for
272 concentrations above $125 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil}_{\text{dw}}$. Atrophy or detachment of gut epithelium was also
273 observed (Figures 3b-e) on earthworms exposed to MPs in the OCDE soil. The occurrence of
274 clear inflammatory processes, between the gut epithelium and the chloragogeneous tissue,
275 sometimes with the development of fibrosis and congestion (Figures 3d-f) was recorded for
276 earthworms exposed to concentrations equal or higher than $125 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil}_{\text{dw}}$. Congestion
277 changing from G2 to G3 for concentrations above this one; fibrosis changing from G1 to G3, in
278 125 and $1000 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil}_{\text{dw}}$, respectively. Similar damages were observed, as well, on
279 earthworms from the positive control (agar with MP) (Figure 3b). Despite the differences in
280 exposure pathways, as blue mussels are filter feeder organism, Van Moos et al. (2012) also
281 observed evident histological changes on *Mytilus edulis* upon exposure to high density
282 polyethylene (HDPE) fluff (non-uniformly shaped and grain size $>0 - 80 \mu\text{m}$). A strong
283 inflammatory response occurred by the formation of granulocytoma in the connective tissue of
284 the digestive gland and in the periphery of ducts and tubules, after 6h of exposure, followed by
285 lysosomes destabilization.

286 ***Please insert figure 3***

287 The molecular changes in organisms exposed to stressors could be used to understand
288 the responses to stress agents (Muthukaruppan, 2015). Figure 4 shows the FTIR-ATR spectra of
289 the earthworms after exposure to different concentrations of MP and before exposure. For
290 comparison, the FTIR-ATR spectrum of PE is also shown. The broad band at 3650-3000 cm^{-1}
291 has been identified for O-H bond vibrations from carboxyl, hydroxyl or phenol groups, and
292 from amides' N-H vibrations. The band with a peak at 2851 cm^{-1} was attributed to the CH_2
293 symmetrical stretch, while the band with a peak at 2918 cm^{-1} band was assigned to
294 asymmetrical stretching of the methylene groups, which may be used to monitor lipids. The
295 bands between 1800-1460 cm^{-1} have been identified for proteins with functional groups, amides
296 I and II and the bands between 1450-1260 cm^{-1} have been assigned to proteins and lipids with
297 functional groups, CH_2 and CH_3 , as well as phosphate compounds with the functional group
298 P=O. The 1260-1180 cm^{-1} bands correspond to polysaccharides with C-O-C and C-O-P
299 functional groups.

300 The small indentation band at 1745–1720 cm^{-1} , as well as those at 1600 cm^{-1} and
301 around 1575–1540 cm^{-1} and 1390-1375 cm^{-1} are characteristic of COO^- ions. Absorption at
302 1620-1660 cm^{-1} is typical of aromatic C=C vibrations, in addition to quinines, conjugated
303 carboxyls and ketones. No clear differences are shown between earthworms exposed to the
304 different concentrations of MP, for these wavenumber intervals however, all the peak areas are
305 greater than that recorded for CTL earthworms. The peak at $\approx 1540 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to amide II
306 structures. The small band at 1462-1454 cm^{-1} can be attributed to symmetric C-H deformation
307 from groups CH_2 and O-H deformation and C-O elongation from phenolic groups. The band
308 with a peak at 1230 cm^{-1} is related to that observed at around 1745-1720 cm^{-1} and it is
309 consistent with C-O elongations and O-H deformations from carboxyl groups. Absorption at
310 1150 cm^{-1} was assigned to $-\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching and CH_2- bending, whereas the band at 1070 cm^{-1}
311 was attributed to $-\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching. The small band at 810 cm^{-1} relates to C-H bending and the
312 more pronounced band at 730 – 600 cm^{-1} pertains to C=C (alkene) bending.

313 ***Please insert figure 4***

314 Bands intensities differed, in particular when comparing the exposed organisms and
315 those in the control group. Generally, a trend consistent with an increase in protein, lipids and
316 polysaccharides with increasing amounts of MPs was identifiable. Table 1 shows the FTIR-
317 ATR bands and corresponding areas for each test group. The principal components analysis
318 (PCA) performed based on FTIR-ATR areas for each wavenumber interval (cm^{-1}), showed that
319 the two first components accounted for 98.3% of the variability of earthworms exposed to the
320 different MPs concentration in the OECD soil. The plot of data shows a clear separation of all
321 the treatments (positive side of component 1) from the CTL (negative side of component 1)
322 (Figure 5). The treatment with the highest concentration of MPs was also set apart from the
323 others, through component 2 (Figure 5). The increased content in protein, lipids and
324 polysaccharides may have been caused by multiple stress-response mechanisms of the immune
325 system of earthworms, involving a wide range of molecules/enzymes, with a role on
326 mechanisms that have evolved for other stress agents. Coelomocytes are responsible for
327 synthesizing immunoprotective molecules, which compose the coelomic fluid of earthworms,
328 like glycoproteins of lectin, which bind carbohydrates required for the immobilization and
329 recognition of foreign bodies, as well as proteases responsible for the activation of enzyme
330 cascades that will degrade foreign material (Kauschke et al., 2007). Further, changes in degree
331 of saturation of fatty acids have also been suggested as a biomarker for the response of soil
332 organisms to stress (Antisari et al., 2014). An increase in saturated fatty acids makes membranes
333 more viscous and less permeable, while on the other hand saturation reduces the susceptibility
334 of fatty acids to free radicals (García et al., 2005). Some of these biomarkers have to be assessed
335 in the future to confirm, the results provided by FTIR-ATR analysis in this study.

336 *Please Insert Table 1*

337 *Please insert figure 5*

338 In summary, although only a few studies have reported the effects of MPs in marine
339 invertebrates (especially for benthic and epi-benthic detritivores species with similar exposure
340 pathways) the expected effects are not different for soil invertebrates, and the consequences will

341 be similar in terms of ecosystems functions and services. Microplastics are likely only one more
342 stress agent occurring in soils, which are able to induce tissue injury (von Moos et al., 2012).
343 Although no reproduction effects were recorded in this study, it is highly probable that this
344 emergent stress agent will contribute for changes in energy allocation in earthworms, with
345 subsequent impacts on populations and on the services for which they are responsible. The
346 presence of MPs in soils, may also change the activity of these “soil engineers”, with
347 subsequent effects on its functions in this compartment (e.g. soil fertility, aeration etc.).
348 Corroborating this hypothesis, Besseling et al. (2013), on their study, also found a significant
349 negative effect of MPs on the activity of lugworms (*A. marina*), in the treatments with 0.074,
350 0.74 and 7.4% by wet weight of sediment. Furthermore, it will become increasingly difficult to
351 predict the risks of MP in soils, using earthworms, as they are apparently able to, at least in part,
352 select their food (as suggested by the results of our positive CTL), and also to prevent more
353 pronounced damages through egestion of MPs (Lwanga et al., 2016). However, more studies are
354 necessary to study, several aspects related with soil organisms, as feeding selectivity, the
355 impacts of particles with even smaller sizes, the interaction of MPs with other soil
356 contaminants, as well as the impacts of MPs in soil structure and functions.

357

358

359 **Acknowledgements**

360 A. Rodríguez-Seijo thanks the University of Vigo for his pre-doctoral fellowship (P.P. 00VI
361 131H 64102) and short stay fellowship (P.P. 00VI 131H 481.02 Bolsa de viaxe). The
362 Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), through National Funds (Ministry
363 for Science and Education in Portugal), provided financial support to Joana Lourenço by means
364 of a Post-Doc grant (SFRH/BPD/92554/2013). This research was also partially supported by the
365 Strategic Funding UID/Multi/04423/2013 through national funds provided by FCT –
366 Foundation for Science and Technology and European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), in

367 the framework of the program PT2020. Financial support to CESAM (UID/AMB/50017/2013),
368 from FCT/MEC through national funds (IF/00407/2013/CP1162/CT0023), and co-funding by
369 the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and Compete 2020 is acknowledged.

370

371 Figures and Table captions

372

373 Figure 1. A) FTIR-ATR spectrum of the polyethylene pellets. In B), an optical image of the MP
374 fragments used is shown (amplification 100X). Note the variable size and shape, as well as their
375 optical hue. The typical surface morphology of the aforementioned particles, as obtained by
376 SEM is shown in C).

377 Figure 2. Optical microscope image (amplification 100X) of the gut content of earthworms
378 grown at a concentration of 1000 mg.kg⁻¹ of MP. The identified MP particulates are
379 highlighted.

380

381 Figure 3. Images (HE) of the transversal mid-section of earthworms: a) exposed to the OECD
382 soil without MP (CTL) with a normal gut epithelium with microvilli and a normal circular
383 muscle surrounding the epithelium (original magnification X100); b) exposed to MPs in agar
384 (positive CTL) showing detachment of the gut epithelium from the circular muscle layer,
385 serious signs of inflammation and alteration of the chloragogeneous tissue (black arrows)
386 (original magnification X200); c) exposed to the 62.5 mg/kg⁻¹ of MPs in OECD soil displaying
387 evidences of MPs in the gut content (black circle) (original magnification X100); d) exposed to
388 125 mg/kg⁻¹ of MPs in OECD soil showing inflammation (G3) and fibrosis (G2), causing
389 hypertrophy of the gut wall and alteration of the chloragogeneous tissue and congestion (G2)
390 (black arrows) (original amplification x100); e) exposed to 500 mg/kg⁻¹ of MPs in OECD soil
391 showing detachment of the gut epithelium from the circular muscle layer and signs of

392 inflammation in the gut wall (G2) and congestion (G2) (black arrows) (original amplification
 393 x100); f) exposed to 1000 mg/kg⁻¹ of MPs in OECD soil showing signs of inflammation (G3)
 394 and congestion (G2) in the gut wall (black arrows) (original amplification x 100).

395

396 Figure 4. FTIR-ATR spectra of the earthworms after exposure to different concentrations of MP
 397 (62.5 mg/kg⁻¹, 125 mg/kg⁻¹, 500 mg/kg⁻¹, 1000 mg/kg⁻¹) and without exposure to MP (MP_0).
 398 For comparison, the FTIR-ATR spectrum of PE is shown.

399

400 Figure 5. PCA plot of the different microplastic treatments based on FTIR-ATR areas obtained
 401 for earthworms.

402

403 Table 1 – FTIR-ATR areas for the spectra of the organisms exposed to MPs and control group.

Wavenumber interval (cm ⁻¹)	MP_0	MP_62.5	MP_125	MP_500	MP_1000	Band identification
3650-3000	43.44	93.89	84.18	80.63	79.27	O-H and N-H vibrations
3000-2810	13.89	27.32	23.23	26.05	25.87	CH ₂ symmetrical stretch (peak at 2851 cm ⁻¹) asymmetrical stretching of methylene groups (peak at 2918 cm ⁻¹)
1800-1460	34.67	81.63	71.87	75.61	63.56	Proteins with functional groups amides I and II
1450-1260	17.28	38.19	33.98	34.66	31.93	Proteins and lipids with functional groups CH ₂ and CH ₃ and phosphate

						compounds with the functional group P=O
1260-1180	6.28	12.62	11.14	12.87	11.33	Polysaccharides C-O-C and C-O-P functional groups
1180-875	27.14	55.21	53.93	51.35	54.33	-C-O stretching and CH ₂ -bending (peak at 1150 cm ⁻¹); -C-O stretching (peak at 1070 cm ⁻¹); C-H bending (peak at 810 cm ⁻¹)
740-580	8.61	12.51	9.94	11.48	13.74	C=C (alkene) bending (peak at 730 - 600 cm ⁻¹)

404

405

406

407 **References**

408 Antisari, L.V., Laudicina, V.A., Gatti, A., Carbone, S., Badalucco, L., Vianello, G., 2014. Soil
 409 microbial biomass carbon and fatty acid composition of earthworm *Lumbricus rubellus*
 410 after exposure to engineered nanoparticles. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 51, 261–269.
 411 doi:10.1007/s00374-014-0972-1

412 Au, S.Y., Bruce, T.F., Bridges, W.C., Klaine, S.J., 2015. Responses of *Hyalella azteca* to acute
 413 and chronic microplastic exposures. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 34, 2564–2572.
 414 doi:10.1002/etc.3093

415 Besseling, E., Wegner, A., Foekema, E.M., van den Heuvel-Greve, M.J., Koelmans, A.A., 2013.
 416 Effects of microplastic on fitness and PCB bioaccumulation by the lugworm *Arenicola*
 417 *marina* (L.). *Env. Sci Technol* 47.

418 Browne, M.A., Niven, S.J., Galloway, T.S., Rowland, S.J., Thompson, R.C., 2013. Microplastic
 419 moves pollutants and additives to worms, reducing functions linked to health and
 420 biodiversity. *Curr Biol* 23.

421 Button, M., Jenkin, G.R.T., Bowman, K.J., Harrington, C.F., Brewer, T.S., Jones, G.D.D.,
 422 Watts, M.J., 2010. DNA damage in earthworms from highly contaminated soils: Assessing
 423 resistance to arsenic toxicity by use of the Comet assay. *Mutat. Res. Genet. Toxicol.*
 424 *Environ. Mutagen.* 696, 95–100.

425 Carson, H.S., Colbert, S.L., Kaylor, M.J., McDermid, K.J., 2011. Small plastic debris changes
 426 water movement and heat transfer through beach sediments. *Mar Pollut Bull* 62.

427 Claessens, M., Meester, S., Landuyt, L., Clerck, K., Janssen, C.R., 2011. Occurrence and
 428 distribution of microplastics in marine sediments along the Belgian coast. *Mar Pollut Bull*
 429 62.

430 Clause, J., Margerie, P., Langlois, E., Decaëns, T., Forey, E., 2011. Fat but slim: Criteria of seed

- 431 attractiveness for earthworms. *Pedobiologia* (Jena). 54, Supple, S159–S165.
432 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2011.08.007>
- 433 Cózar, A., Echevarría, F., González-Gordillo, J.I., Irigoien, X., Ubeda, B., Hernández-León, S.,
434 2014. Plastic debris in the open ocean. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 111.
- 435 Curry, J.P., Schmidt, O., 2007. The feeding ecology of earthworms – A review. *Pedobiologia*
436 (Jena). 50, 463–477. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2006.09.001>
- 437 Dris, R., Gasperi, J., Saad, M., Mirande, C., Tassin, B., 2016. Synthetic fibers in atmospheric
438 fallout: A source of microplastics in the environment? *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 104, 290–293.
439 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.01.006>
- 440 Duis, K., Coors, A., 2016. Microplastics in the aquatic and terrestrial environment: sources
441 (with a specific focus on personal care products), fate and effects. *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 28, 1–
442 25. doi:10.1186/s12302-015-0069-y
- 443 Espí, E., Salmerón, A., Fontecha, A., García, Y., Real, A.I., 2006. PLastic Films for
444 Agricultural Applications. *J. Plast. Film Sheeting* 22, 85–102.
445 doi:10.1177/8756087906064220
- 446 FAOUN, 1984. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations — Physical and
447 chemical methods of soil and water analysis. *Soils Bull.* 10, 1–275.
- 448 García, J.J., Martínez-Ballarín, E., Millán-Plano, S., Allué, J.L., Albendea, C., Fuentes, L.,
449 Escanero, J.F., 2005. Effects of trace elements on membrane fluidity. *J. Trace Elem. Med.*
450 *Biol.* 19, 19–22. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2005.07.007>
- 451 Gavina, A., Bouguerra, S., Lopes, I., Marques, C.R., Rasteiro, M.G., Antunes, F., Rocha-Santos,
452 T., Pereira, R., 2016. Impact of organic nano-vesicles in soil: The case of sodium dodecyl
453 sulphate/didodecyl dimethylammonium bromide. *Sci. Total Environ.* 547, 413–421.
454 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.163>
- 455 Green, D.S., Boots, B., Sigwart, J., Jiang, S., Rocha, C., 2016. Effects of conventional and
456 biodegradable microplastics on a marine ecosystem engineer (*Arenicola marina*) and
457 sediment nutrient cycling. *Environ. Pollut.* 208, Part, 426–434.
458 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2015.10.010>
- 459 ISO, 2008. Soil quality -- Avoidance test for determining the quality of soils and effects of
460 chemicals on behaviour -- Part 1: Test with earthworms (*Eisenia fetida* and *Eisenia*
461 *andrei*). 17512-1.
- 462 ISO, 1998. Soil Quality – Effects of pollutants on earthworms. Part 2: Determination of effects
463 on reproduction on earthworms (*Eisenia fetida*). No.11268-2.
- 464 ISO, 1996. Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on earthworms (*Eisenia fetida*) -- Part 2:
465 Determination of effects on reproduction. No. 11268-2.
- 466 Jager, T., Fleuren, R.H.L.J., Roelofs, W., de Groot, A.C., 2003. Feeding activity of the
467 earthworm *Eisenia andrei* in artificial soil. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 35, 313–322.
468 doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(02\)00282-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(02)00282-1)
- 469 Kauschke, E., Mohrig, W., Cooper, E.L., 2007. Coelomic fluid proteins as basic components of

470 innate immunity in earthworms. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 43, Supple, S110–S115.
471 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2007.08.043>

472 Lambert, S., Sinclair, C., Boxall, A., 2014. Reviews of Environmental Contamination and
473 Toxicology, Volume 227, in: Whitacre, M.D. (Ed.), . Springer International Publishing,
474 Cham, pp. 1–53. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-01327-5_1

475 Lassen, C., Hansen, S.F., Magnusson, K., Hartmann, N.B., Rehne Jensen, P., Nielsen, T.G.,
476 Brinch, A., 2015. Microplastics (RPRT), Occurrence, effects and sources of releases to the
477 environment in Denmark. Danish Environmental Protection Agency.

478 Lavelle, P., Bignell, D., Lepage, M., Wolters, V., Roger, P., Ineson, P., Heal, O.W., Dhillion, S.,
479 1997. Soil function in a changing world: the role of invertebrate ecosystem engineers. *Eur.*
480 *J. Soil Biol.* 33, 159–193.

481 Lwanga, E., Gertsen, H., Gooren, H., Peters, P., Salánki, T., van der Ploeg, M., Besseling, E.,
482 Koelmans, A.A., Geissen, V., 2016. Microplastics in the Terrestrial Ecosystem:
483 Implications for *Lumbricus terrestris* (Oligochaeta, Lumbricidae). *Environ. Sci. Technol.*
484 50, 2685–2691. doi:10.1021/acs.est.5b05478

485 Muthukaruppan, G., 2015. Heavy metal induced biomolecule and genotoxic changes in
486 earthworm *Eisenia fetida*. *ISJ* 12, 237–245.

487 OECD, 2004. Earthworm reproduction test (*Eisenia fetida/andrei*). OECD Guidel. Test. Chem.
488 1, 1–18.

489 OECD, 1984. Earthworm, Acute Toxicity Tests. OECD Guidel. Test. Chem. 1, 1–9.

490 Ogonowski, M., Schür, C., Jarsén, Å., Gorokhova, E., 2016. The Effects of Natural and
491 Anthropogenic Microparticles on Individual Fitness in *Daphnia magna*. *PLoS One* 11,
492 e0155063.

493 Pokarzhevskii, A.D., Van Straalen, N.M., Semenov, A.M., 2000. Agar as a medium for
494 removing soil from earthworm guts. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 32, 1315–1317.
495 doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(00\)00018-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(00)00018-3)

496 Ramos, L., Berenstein, G., Hughes, E.A., Zalts, A., Montserrat, J.M., 2015. Polyethylene film
497 incorporation into the horticultural soil of small periurban production units in Argentina.
498 *Sci. Total Environ.* 523, 74–81. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.03.142>

499 Rillig, M.C., 2012. Microplastic in terrestrial ecosystems and the soil? *Env. Sci Technol* 46.

500 Rocha-Santos, T., Duarte, A.C., 2015. A critical overview of the analytical approaches to the
501 occurrence, the fate and the behavior of microplastics in the environment. *TrAC Trends*
502 *Anal. Chem.* 65, 47–53. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2014.10.011>

503 Shumway, D.L., Koide, R.T., 1994. Seed preferences of *Lumbricus terrestris* L. *Appl. Soil Ecol.*
504 1, 11–15. doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0929-1393\(94\)90019-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0929-1393(94)90019-1)

505 Steinmetz, Z., Wollmann, C., Schaefer, M., Buchmann, C., David, J., Tröger, J., Muñoz, K.,
506 Frör, O., Schaumann, G.E., 2016. Plastic mulching in agriculture. Trading short-term
507 agronomic benefits for long-term soil degradation? *Sci. Total Environ.* 550, 690–705.
508 doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.01.153

- 509 Thompson, R.C., Olsen, Y., Mitchell, R.P., Davis, A., Rowland, S.J., John, A.W., 2004. Lost at
510 sea: where is all the plastic? *Science* (80-.). 304, 838.
- 511 von Moos, N., Burkhardt-Holm, P., Köhler, A., 2012. Uptake and Effects of Microplastics on
512 Cells and Tissue of the Blue Mussel *Mytilus edulis* L. after an Experimental Exposure.
513 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46, 11327–11335. doi:10.1021/es302332w
- 514 Woodall, L.C., Sanchez-Vidal, A., Canals, M., Paterson, G.L.J., Coppock, R., Sleight, V., 2014.
515 The deep sea is a major sink for microplastic debris. *R Soc Open Sci* 1.
- 516 Wright, S.L., Thompson, R.C., Galloway, T.S., 2013. The physical impacts of microplastics on
517 marine organisms: a review. *Env. Pollut* 178.
- 518 Zaller, J.G., Saxler, N., 2007. Selective vertical seed transport by earthworms: Implications for
519 the diversity of grassland ecosystems. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 43, Supple, S86–S91.
520 doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2007.08.010>
- 521

Table A. Average of survival, weight loss and juveniles of *E. andrei* exposed to different concentrations of microplastics (Mean \pm standard deviation).

	Concentration of microplastics (mg kg ⁻¹)					
	0 (control)	62.5	125	250	500	1000
Survival (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100
Weight loss (%) relative to CTL	-	25.09 \pm 13.91	20.88 \pm 12.95	22.83 \pm 12.71	30.19 \pm 7.89	33.1 \pm 13.67
CV weight	-	0.55	0.62	0.55	0.26	0.41
Juveniles (no.)	45 \pm 3.56	50.75 \pm 15.13	51.75 \pm 8.34	54.50 \pm 10.15	47.50 \pm 7.42	47 \pm 11.37
Reproduction rate (no. juveniles/10 adult earthworms)	4.50 \pm 0.36	5.88 \pm 1.15	5.18 \pm 0.83	5.45 \pm 1.01	4.75 \pm 0.74	4.70 \pm 1.13
CV juveniles (d28)	0.07	0.29	0.16	0.18	0.20	0.24

CV Coefficient variation (standard deviation/mean). The percentage of weight loss was calculated relatively to the control.

Figure A1-2. Representative images of microplastics milling, in a handmade electrical mill.

Figure B – Figure 3c with a higher amplification (original amplification X200).